

CAREER: Intelligent Representations: How to Blend Physical and Virtual Representations by Adapting to the Individual Student's Needs in Real Time

Project Description

1 Statement of Problem

Science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) domains rely on visual representations: Mathematicians plot functions; chemists build models of molecules. Therefore, a key aspect of STEM instruction is to help students learn *representation skills*: understanding how representations depict information and connecting different representations (Gilbert, 2008; Rau, 2016). *Physical and virtual representation modes* have different conceptual and embodied affordances for students' learning (Johnson-Glenberg, Birchfield, Tolentino, & Koziupa, 2014; Olympiou & Zacharia, 2012). Further, connecting different representation modes fosters learning of domain knowledge (e.g., Antle, Corness, & Droumeva, 2009). For example, helping students connect physical and virtual representations of molecules enhances their understanding of representations and of complex chemistry concepts (Stull & Hegarty, 2016). Yet, there is no comprehensive theory on complementary affordances of physical and virtual representations affect learning of representation skills and domain knowledge. I propose to build such theory and to translate it into a design framework for educational technologies that effectively blend representation modes.

Educational technologies are particularly effective in supporting representation skills because they can adapt in real time to students' needs while they manipulate representations (Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015; VanLehn, 2011). Interventions that support representation skills enhance STEM learning (National Research Council [NRC] 2006; Rau, Aleven, & Rummel, in press). Yet, educational technologies commonly used in STEM instruction rely solely on *virtual representations* presented on a computer screen and manipulated via text or mouse (Figure 1, a-d). By contrast, *blending innovations* (Johnson-Glenberg et al., 2014; Stull & Hegarty, 2016) combine virtual and *physical representations*: tangible objects that students manipulate by hand (Figure 1, e-g). These representation modes have complementary benefits: While virtual representations can show invisible processes, physical representations provide haptic experiences that align with students' real-world experiences (de Jong, Linn, & Zacharia, 2013). Current blending innovations are limited because they tend not to offer adaptive support and rely on complex equipment that is difficult to use in regular educational contexts. Hence, they may add to a digital divide that deprives students of innovations due to socioeconomic factors (NRC, 2012; Witte, Kiss, & Lynn, 2013).

Because educational technologies are limited to virtual representations, instructors who combine representation modes have to sequence technology-based activities and separate hands-on activities. Such simple combinations are likely ineffective: For example, research findings conflict as to whether physical-virtual or virtual-physical sequences are most effective (e.g., Jaakkola & Nurmi, 2008). Effects depend on concepts (e.g., Gire et al., 2010), motor actions (Antle et al., 2009), and learning progress (Horn, Crouser, & Bers, 2012). Hence, effective combinations of representation modes are likely too complex for instructors to achieve without support. Educational technologies can offer such support: They can use computational (cognitive) models to adapt instruction to concepts, actions, and learning progress. What prevents designers from developing adaptive educational technologies that intelligently blend virtual and physical representations is (1) a lack of coherent theory about how representation modes complement one another, and (2) technologies' inability to interface with physical representations.

Figure 1. Physical representations (top) and virtual representations (bottom).

2 Proposed Research Program

The goal of my 5-year CAREER project is to address these shortcomings. To this end, I will develop a theory that describes how complementary affordances of representation modes affect students' learning of representation skills and domain knowledge. I will use this theory to develop a design framework for educational technologies that intelligently blend physical and virtual representations while adapting to student needs. Partnerships with instructors will ensure the technologies are usable in real education contexts.

To achieve this goal, I propose *research activities* that comprise a series of user-centered studies and controlled experiments. The research activities draw on embodied learning theory as a potential missing link that may explain the concept-specific, action-specific, and learner-specific effects in prior studies. Three experiments investigate open questions about complementary conceptual and embodied affordances of physical and virtual representations. I will use these findings to develop theory-based principles describing how best to combine physical and virtual representations in real educational contexts (e.g., homework, classroom) depending on the concept, the student's motor actions, and learning progress.

Interleaved with these research activities, *development activities* will use a user-centered approach to develop an intelligent blending technology for chemistry courses at 2-year and 4-year colleges. I will work closely with instructors and students to ensure the educational technology addresses educational needs and systemic constraints in their context. The resulting educational technology will adapt to student needs based on a computational (cognitive) model. The model formalizes principles emerging from the research activities in an educational technology that optimally combines physical and virtual representations. A final experiment will test the intelligent blending framework in a different domain and context.

I situate this 5-year project in *undergraduate chemistry* for the following reasons. First, enhancing students' representation skills is a major goal in chemistry education (Cheng & Gilbert, 2009; NRC, 2006) because students' difficulties in using representations jeopardize their learning (Dori & Barak, 2001; Talanquer, 2013). Second, the role of representations in chemistry is similar to other STEM domains: They illustrate abstract concepts (Justi & Gilbert, 2002) and play a key role in discipline discourse (Airey & Linder, 2009; Uttal & O'Doherty, 2008). Thus, my findings may generalize to other STEM domains.

Further, I situate my 5-year CAREER project in the context of an effective type of educational technology: *intelligent tutoring systems* (ITSs) (Koedinger & Corbett, 2006; VanLehn, 2011) for the following reasons. First, ITSs can provide adaptive support for interactive representations that helps students acquire representation skills, thereby helping them learn domain knowledge (Rau, Aleven, & Rummel, in press). Second, they support learning through problem solving, which aligns with STEM education practices—including chemistry (Bodner & Domin, 2000; Wu & Shah, 2004). Finally, ITSs are effective when used in regular instruction in K-16 contexts (Koedinger & Corbett, 2006; Rau, 2015b; VanLehn, 2011).

My *education plan* lays the foundation for expanding my research on intelligent blending to other STEM domains and contexts by examining roles of representation modes in K-12 contexts. Further, my education plan will investigate effective pathways toward embedding intelligent blending technologies in college courses and K-12 classrooms and disseminating these technologies to diverse populations. To this end, I propose a series of inter-related education activities that involve instructors early in the project so as to learn and design for their instructional and systemic needs, and to build lasting partnerships.

Thus, this project will help me achieve my *long-term research goal* to (1) build theory about how different representation modes engage complementary learning processes when students use representations to learn about abstract concepts, and (2) to develop design frameworks that guide the development of a new genre of educational technologies that leverage this theory to intelligently blend multiple learning modes by adapting to the individual student's needs. Because physical and virtual representations play a key role in STEM learning, intelligent blending has the potential to transform STEM education.

3 Theoretical Background and Open Research Questions

3.1 Representation Skills are Prerequisite to Success in Chemistry

In chemistry, as in many STEM domains, many concepts cannot be observed with the regular eye (Gilbert, 2008; Uttal & O'Doherty, 2008). Hence, instruction uses visual representations to illustrate these concepts (Kozma & Russell, 2005; Stieff, 2007). To succeed in chemistry, students need representation

skills (Ainsworth, 2008; Gilbert, 2004; Rau, 2016): They need to understand how representations depict information: which visual features are relevant (e.g., the size of spheres in space-filling model show the Van der Waals volume; Figure 1-b/f) and which are incidental (e.g., red color of oxygen does not mean the atom is red; Figure 1-b/f) (Ainsworth, 2006; Schnotz, 2005). Students also need to understand connections among representations: how they show corresponding concepts (e.g., a line in Figure 1-a corresponds to a button pair in Figure 1-e because a bond is a shared electron pair) and complementary information (e.g., the button pairs show which atom the electrons belong to, but the line does not).

Abundant evidence documents that students' lack of representation skills results in numerous misconceptions about atomic structure and bonding (Cooper, Corley, & Underwood, 2013; Kozma, Chin, Russell, & Marx, 2000; Strickland, Kraft, & Bhattacharyya, 2010). Interventions that help students understand how representations visualize concepts have been shown to improve learning of chemistry knowledge (Davidowitz & Chittleborough, 2009; Linenberger & Bretz, 2012; Rau, 2015a). Further, physical and virtual representations have complementary benefits that can help students understand how representations show concepts (Abraham, Varghese, & Tang, 2010; Barrett, Stull, Hsu, & Hegarty, 2015; Kozma, 1994). Moreover, helping students connect these representation modes enhances their learning of chemistry concepts (Dori & Barak, 2001). Thus, my *research goal* for this 5-year CAREER project is to build theory describing how physical and virtual representations afford complementary learning processes as students use the representations to make sense of abstract chemistry concepts. This theory will yield principles that can inform the design of effective interventions that leverage these complementary affordances in a way that enhances students' learning of chemistry knowledge.

3.2 Combining Physical and Virtual Representations

3.2.1 *Explicit Conceptual Affordances of Physical and Virtual Representations*

In chemistry, as in many STEM domains, instruction uses physical and virtual representations (Manches & O'Malley, 2012; Stull, Gainer, Padalkar, & Hegarty, 2016). Whether a physical or virtual representation is more effective seems to depend on its conceptual affordances: that is, whether it makes a concept salient (Chini, Madsen, Gire, Rebello, & Puntambekar, 2012; Gire et al., 2010). Building on these results, Olympiou and Zacharia (2012) offer a blending framework that matches representations to concepts based on their conceptual affordances. An experiment compared two control conditions with only physical or virtual representations and a combined condition in which physical and virtual representations were matched to concepts. The combined condition showed higher learning gains.

A limitation of this experiment is that it confounded matching of representation mode to concept with number of representation modes. Students in the control conditions received only one representation mode. There was no control condition that received multiple "unmatched" representation modes. A further limitation is that Olympiou and Zacharia's blending framework focuses on a very specific set of concepts but offers no comprehensive theory that would allow instructors to determine affordances a priori. Finally, the blending framework does not take into account embodied affordances of representations.

3.2.2 *Implicit Embodied Affordances of Physical and Virtual Representations*

I propose that a missing link between concept-specific effects and comprehensive theory about affordances of representation modes are their embodied affordances: their ability to invoke students' implicit embodied knowledge. *Embodied learning theory* holds that knowledge emerges from the body's interactions in the real world; understanding of even the most abstract concept (e.g., valency, polarity) has its roots in embodied action (Barsalou, 2008; Glenberg, 2010; Wilson, 2002). When students learn a new concept, they form a mental simulation that is grounded in real experiences (Abrahamson & Lindgren, 2014; Clark, 2013). For example, students may mentally simulate a chemical bond as a physical object such as a pipeline for electrons; a common misconception among undergraduate students (Nicoll, 2001).

Embodied learning theory explains the fact that representation modes have complementary advantages by examining the nature of motor actions and embodied metaphors they invoke (Johnson-Glenberg et al., 2014; Nemirovsky et al., 2004). Embodied metaphors are implicitly acquired action schemas that result from sensory-motor experiences with our body's movements and interactions in the real world (e.g., upward movement invokes concepts related to fullness, improvement, happiness; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980).

Studies show that representations can enhance learning by invoking action schemas and embodied metaphors that are consistent with target concepts (Abrahamson & Lindgren, 2014; Antle, Corness, & Droumeva, 2009; Bamberger & diSessa, 2003). Thus, embodied theory suggests that physical and virtual representations can invoke different motor actions and metaphors that may (or may not) be consistent with the concept (Abrahamson & Sánchez-García, 2016; Johnson-Glenberg et al., 2014). Motor actions and metaphors that are consistent with the concept can enhance learning of domain knowledge.

For example, a student may represent a polar bond between carbon and oxygen in a physical and virtual ball-and-stick model (Figures 1-c/g). In a polar bond, the more electronegative oxygen attracts electrons from the less electronegative carbon. In the physical ball-and-stick model (Figure 1-c), the student pushes the atoms together to fasten them to either end of the stick. By contrast, in the virtual ball-and-stick model (Figure 1-g), the student drags a line from carbon to oxygen. Hence, the different representation modes invoke different action schemas, and the dragging motion is more consistent with the concept than the pushing motion. Thus, the virtual mode may be more effective for the polarity concept.

If a representation mode's conceptual affordance (i.e., making a concept more salient) align with its implicit embodied affordances (i.e., invoking consistent action schemas), it seems clear which mode to choose. But what if physical and virtual representations have conflicting conceptual and embodied affordances? For example, the physical ball-and-stick model makes valency conceptually salient because the number of holes in spheres corresponds to an atom's valency, indicating how many bonds it can form.

A variety of factors may affect whether embodied affordances are more important than conceptual affordances, or vice versa. First, it has been argued that embodied grounding may be particularly important for students with low prior knowledge (Zacharia, Loizou, & Papaevripidou, 2012). Second, embodied grounding may play a larger role in students' learning of concepts that are concrete, complex, and spatial (Stull & Hegarty, 2016). Such differences between conceptual and embodied affordances may explain why complementary effects of physical and virtual representations depend on the concept and students' learning progress. Because research on representation modes has focused on explicit conceptual affordances while disregarding implicit embodied affordances, this question remains to be addressed:

Research question 1: How does students' prior knowledge and the nature of target concepts affect embodied and conceptual affordances for students' learning?

3.2.3 *Optimally Sequencing Physical and Virtual Representations*

A line of research that has investigated how best to combine representation modes that have complementary benefits for students' learning is *distributed scaffolding*. This research investigates how to optimally combine multiple learning aids ("scaffolds") (Puntambekar, 2015; Puntambekar & Kolodner, 2005). Representations are scaffolds because they help students understand abstract concepts (Vygotsky, 1962, 1978; Wertsch & Kazak, 2011). Studies testing how best to combine representation modes found physical-virtual sequences to be more effective than virtual-physical sequences (Smith & Puntambekar, 2010; Winn et al., 2006). In contrast, others (Jaakkola & Nurmi, 2008; Zacharia & Anderson, 2003) found virtual-physical sequences to be more effective. To resolve these contradictory findings, it has been argued that the optimal sequence depends on conceptual affordances of representation modes (Johnson-Glenberg, Birchfield, Savvides, & Megowan-Romanowicz, 2011; Olympiou & Zacharia, 2012).

My own research aims to uncover the mechanisms of such concept-specific sequence effects. In a recent study (Rau, Wu, & Schuberth, 2016), I tested effects of physical-virtual and virtual-physical sequences on how students collaboratively make sense of chemistry concepts. Physical representations were embedded in hands-on activities without technology support. Virtual representations were embedded in an ITS with adaptive support for representation skills. Results suggest that students who started with physical representations engaged in more productive conceptual reasoning, whereas students who started with virtual representations engaged in more shallow reasoning. Yet, students worked more efficiently with virtual than with physical representations. Interestingly, students maintained reasoning patterns after switching: Students working with physical-virtual sequences maintained a high level of conceptual reasoning when switching to virtual representations, whereas students working with virtual-physical sequences maintained shallow reasoning when switching to physical representations. An explanation for

this effect may be that students maintain reasoning patterns afforded by the first representation mode.

My study suggests that starting with a representation mode with affordances appropriate for a novice student and switching to a representation mode that has complementary affordances may be most effective. However, my prior study did not account for embodied affordances and did not systematically test effects on learning outcomes. Further, prior research on distributed scaffolding has not investigated the effects of implicit embodied affordances of representation modes. Hence, an open question is:

Research question 2: How do conceptual and embodied affordances affect which sequence of physical and virtual representations is most effective for students' learning of concepts?

3.2.4 Supporting Connection Making between Representations

Research on representation skills indicates that students' learning critically depends on their ability to make connections among representations (Ainsworth, 2006; Bodemer & Faust, 2006). Because connection-making is difficult, students tend not to make connections spontaneously (Ainsworth, Bibby, & Wood, 2002; Rau, Alevin, Rummel, & Pardos, 2014). Hence, they need support to do so (Bodemer & Faust, 2006; Gilbert, 2005; Rau, 2016). Educational technologies can be effective in supporting connection making (e.g., de Jong & van Joolingen, 1998; Rau, Alevin, & Rummel, in press; Reimer & Moyer, 2005). A limitation of this research is that it has focused on virtual representations alone.

Few studies have investigated how to use educational technologies to support connection making between physical and virtual representations. In a recent experiment, I tested whether prompting students to connect physical ball-and-stick models and virtual Lewis structures is effective (Rau, Bowman, & Moore, under review). Students constructed a virtual Lewis structure using an ITS for chemistry. If students made an error, the ITS highlighted the error in the virtual representation (e.g., a bond) and prompted them to use a physical ball-and-stick model to fix the error. Students who received this connection-making support showed significantly higher learning gains than a control group without connection-making support.

Research on blended learning innovations has investigated novel ways to support connection making. Physical representations enhanced with digital features can communicate changes to a virtual representation that updates to show corresponding changes. Students make connections by manipulating virtual representations via the *enhanced physical representation*. To design enhanced representations, this research draws on embodied metaphors to help students connect the representation modes (Antle et al., 2009; Bakker, Antle, & Van Den Hoven, 2012; Horn, Crouser, & Bers, 2012; Stull & Hegarty, 2016). While these studies show positive effects of enhanced physical representations on students' learning, other studies suggest that they may not always be effective (Smith, King, & Hoyte, 2014; Skulmowski, Pradel, Kühnert, Brunnett, & Rey, 2016): The effectiveness of enhanced physical representations depends on whether the motor actions engage metaphors that are consistent with the to-be-learned concepts, and whether students can connect their motor actions to concepts.

Evaluations of enhanced physical representations are limited in several ways. First, this research has not compared enhanced physical representations to control conditions in which students received physical and virtual representations without connection-making support. Second, research on enhanced representations and my own prior study confound representation type with representation mode (e.g., virtual Lewis structure vs. physical ball-and-stick model, Figure 1-a/g). On the one hand, connecting representations of the same type (e.g., virtual and physical Lewis structure, Figure 1-a/e) may be *ineffective* because they share many surface features, which may prompt spontaneous connection making. In this case, explicit connection-making support may interfere with student learning because this "over-scaffolding" is a waste of instructional time and may annoy students. On the other hand, it may be *effective* because abundant evidence (e.g., Ainsworth et al., 2002; Rau et al., 2014) suggests that students tend to not spontaneously connect different representation types (e.g., virtual Lewis structure vs. virtual ball-and-stick model). Further, recall the earlier argument that switching representation mode may allow students to maintain reasoning patterns afforded by the first mode while taking advantage of the second mode. Helping students explicitly connect representation modes may strengthen their ability to maintain affordances from the first representation mode after switching. Hence, we need to address:

Research question 3: How does support to make connections among physical and virtual representations help students take advantage of conceptual and embodied affordances?

3.3 Intelligent Tutoring Systems as a Research Platform for Intelligent Blending

ITSs are a suitable platform to address these research questions. ITSs can adapt instruction to the target concept, the individual student's learning progress and actions (Koedinger & Corbett, 2006; VanLehn, 2011). To do so, ITSs use a cognitive model that infers whether the student has learned target skills based on her/his interactions with the technology (Anderson, Boyle, Corbett, & Lewis, 1990). Based on an ongoing diagnosis of the student's learning progress, the ITS provides adaptive support via hints, error feedback, and selection of appropriate activities—key behaviors of effective human instructors (VanLehn, 2011). While most research on ITSs has focused on domain knowledge, my research has focused on supporting and adapting to representation skills, which in turn enhances learning of domain knowledge. My research shows that ITSs that enhance representation skills increase learning outcomes in fourth- through seventh-grade math (Rau, Aleven, & Rummel, 2015) and college chemistry (Rau, 2015a; Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015). Yet, because ITSs cannot interface with physical representations, we need to address:

Development goal: Develop a design framework for educational technologies that leverages complementary affordances of different representation modes while adapting to individual student needs.

4 Research Plan

The goal of this project is to enhance chemistry learning by helping students understand visual representations. To do so, I will develop an intelligent blending framework that extends the adaptive capabilities of ITSs to physical representations. Three experiments will address my research questions, yielding:

- theory about complementary affordances of physical and virtual representations;
- principles to combine representation modes based on their conceptual and embodied affordances;
- intelligent sequences of physical and virtual representations that adapt to individual students' needs;
- support for connection making between physical and virtual representations.

4.1 Building on Prior Research: Chem Tutor

The proposed research builds on Chem Tutor, an ITS for undergraduate chemistry, developed and tested in my lab (Rau, 2015a). Chem Tutor will serve as a platform for this research. My team designed it based on a user-centered approach (Rau, under review; Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015) that involved experienced chemistry instructors in the design of activities. The activities address misconceptions identified in user-studies with students. Chem Tutor activities build on one another in a way that aligns with chemistry learning progressions (Johnson, 2013). The curriculum covers a comprehensive set of about 50 concepts that vary in terms of abstractness, complexity, and spatial nature. These concepts are typically covered in general chemistry courses and align with the American Chemical Society (2009, 2015) standards for 2-year and 4-year programs and advanced 9–12th grade content standards (NRC, 1996, 2013). Chem Tutor includes virtual representations common in chemistry education (Cooper, Underwood, Hilley, & Klymkowsky, 2012) and provides adaptive support for representation skills. Chem Tutor was evaluated in lab studies and field studies situated in introductory chemistry courses (Rau, 2015a; Rau & Wu, 2015; Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015) and showed significant gains in chemistry knowledge with large effect sizes of $d = 1.02$ to $d = 1.32$. Chem Tutor is available for free at <https://chem.tutorshop.web.cmu.edu/>.

4.2 Phase 1: Choosing Physical and Virtual Representations

The first step in developing the intelligent blending framework is to address **Research question 1:** How does students' prior knowledge and the nature of target concepts affect embodied and conceptual affordances for students' learning? I will establish a methodology that will enable instructors to identify conceptual and embodied affordances of physical and virtual representations a priori. Typically, ITS designers use two types of cognitive task analysis (CTA) to test whether learning activities foster productive processes (Clark, Feldon, Van Merriënboër, Yates, & Early, 2008). Theoretical CTAs ask experts to describe reasoning processes involved in activities; empirical CTAs ask students to “think aloud” while they work on activities (Ericsson & Simon, 1984, 1987). CTAs are currently limited to *explicit* knowledge.

4.2.1 Theoretical Cognitive Task Analyses for Embodied and Conceptual Knowledge

A first step is to expand the theoretical CTA to action schemas and embodied metaphors. To this end, I will partner with expert chemistry instructors to examine Chem Tutor's learning activities with virtual representations for each of the 50 target concepts. For each activity with virtual representations, we will consider a corresponding activity with a physical representation of the same type. To analyze which action schemas the activity may activate, we will examine motor actions used to manipulate the representation. This analysis will draw on the taxonomy by Johnson-Glenberg et al. (2014), which details effective alignments of motor actions and concepts. To analyze which embodied metaphors the activity may invoke, we will examine metaphors stated in the activity and metaphors the expert uses to explain how representations show concepts. To do so, we will draw on research describing how bodily experiences may explain metaphors (e.g., Bakker et al., 2012; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). The CTA will yield hypotheses about whether a representation mode's embodied affordances are consistent with the target concept. In addition, we will use the canonical theoretical CTA approach (Clark et al., 2008) to analyze conceptual affordances of each representation mode. This CTA will yield hypotheses about whether a representation mode's conceptual affordances are consistent with the concepts. In sum, for each concept, the CTAs yield hypotheses about whether conceptual and embodied affordances (1) predict that a physical or (2) a virtual is most effective, or (3) contradict one another (i.e., similar to the polarity examples in 3.2.2).

4.2.2 Experiment

I will combine an empirical CTA (Clark et al., 2008) with an experiment to (1) test the hypotheses that emerged from the CTAs, which (2) serves to evaluate the methodology that will allow instructors to determine conceptual and embodied affordances a priori. **Experiment 1** will use a between-subjects design with random assignment to conditions. In a *match-condition*, students work with the representation mode matched to each concept based on the CTAs. If affordances conflict, embodied affordances will be prioritized. In a *mismatch condition*, students work with opposite representation modes for each concept.

To assess students' *learning outcomes*, I will use a pretest, immediate posttest, and (one week later) a delayed posttest. Each test assesses students' chemistry knowledge for each target concept (reproduction and transfer; Schwartz, Bransford, & Sears, 2005), and representation skills. The tests were developed and iteratively refined based on a learner-centered design approach (Rau, under review; Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015) and were validated with confirmatory factor analyses and item-response theory models on data from $N = 1,199$ undergraduates. Further, I will collect several *learning process measures*. Chem Tutor collects log data on problem-solving behaviors that yield insights into problem-solving strategies and errors. Further, a randomly chosen subset of at least 20% of participants will be asked to think-aloud while working on the activities. Sessions will be video-taped and coded for concepts mentioned, motor actions, metaphors mentioned, and errors made while constructing physical representations.

To *analyze effects on learning outcomes*, I will conduct a multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA) with condition as independent variable, pretest measures as covariates, and posttest measures as dependent variables. Based on the results from the theoretical CTAs, I will create three scales for the chemistry tests for (1) items assessing concepts for which the CTAs predicted the best match to be a physical representation (physical-match items) or (2) a virtual representation would be more effective (virtual-match items), and (3) items assessing concepts for which conceptual and embodied affordances conflicted (conflict items). Comparing the match and mismatch conditions on physical-match and virtual-match items tests the hypotheses from the theoretical CTAs. Comparing conditions on conflict items tests whether embodied or conceptual affordances are more important. In addition, I will use the MANCOVA to test for interactions of conditions with prior knowledge about chemistry and representations. This step will test whether matching is more important for students with low prior knowledge. Further, I will test whether effects depend on the nature of the concepts by comparing abstract vs. concrete, simple vs. complex, and spatial vs. non-spatial concepts. Finally, I will use causal path analysis to test whether representation skills mediate these effects (Rau et al., in press; Rau, Scheines, Alevan, & Rummel, 2013).

In addition, analyses of the *tutor log data* will be used to assess students' learning of each target concept while they work with virtual representations. Of interest is whether students show higher learn rates

when using virtual representations to learn about concepts for which the CTAs predicted the virtual representation would be more effective than a physical representation, rather than vice versa. Further, I will use log data to identify problem-solving steps that were too difficult and showed low learn rates. In collaboration with instructors, I will use these data to iteratively refine activities between experiments.

Finally, I will use the *think-aloud* data to examine whether students engage in motor actions and metaphors that correspond to the ones predicted by the CTAs and whether they are consistent with the concept. These analyses may yield insights into the mechanisms underlying the effects on learning outcomes. Further, if some of the hypothesized effects are not significant, think-alouds may help interpret these effects. For example, student engagement in consistent motor actions with a physical representation even though the CTAs predicted the virtual representation to be the best match may explain a lack of an effect for the given concept and will inform the design of the next experiment (see below). Preliminary results from a pilot study of the theoretical and empirical CTAs support the hypothesis physical representations invoke movement metaphors more so than virtual representations when students learn about polarity.

Experiment 1 will be carried out in my research lab. To recruit participants with a range of prior knowledge levels, I will recruit from chemistry courses at the University of Wisconsin–Madison (UW–Madison), Ph.D. programs in chemistry and related fields, from Madison Area Technical College (MATC; a 2-year college), and—to recruit novices—from programs without chemistry requirements.

Feasibility. To ensure the feasibility of Experiment 1, I explored the statistical power and minimum sample size needed for the experiment. Based on earlier findings (Rau, 2015a; Rau et al., under review), I assumed a medium effect size of $f^2 = 0.25$ for between-subjects effects and a correlation of $\rho = .49$ among dependent measures. An *a priori* power analysis with a maximum type 1 probability of $\alpha = .05$ and two repetitions (i.e., two posttests) for a MANCOVA with pretest performance as covariate and *two* conditions showed that a minimum of $N = 96$ participants are required to achieve a statistical power of $\beta = .80$.

4.2.3 Development

The findings from the theoretical and empirical CTAs will provide insights into complementary effects of representation modes on students' learning of representation skills and domain knowledge. This will provide the basis for a new cognitive model—an algorithm that takes as input the student's interactions with the ITS (e.g., errors during problem solving) and outputs a prediction of his/her learning progress. ITSs use cognitive models to select appropriate activities for the student. For example, if a student draws an incorrect polarity vector, the cognitive model may infer that she has not understood polarity and assign activities that make polarity salient. I will develop a cognitive model based on the CTAs that takes as inputs a student's prior chemistry knowledge and representation skills and the representation's embodied and conceptual affordances. Log data from following experiments will serve to update the model.

The cognitive model needs to assess students' interactions with physical representations. To this end, I will develop a low-fidelity prototype that asks students to self-assess the physical representations by comparing them to correct representations shown on the screen. The prototype serves to pilot-test the cognitive model. It will also provide initial data for a high-fidelity application that will use a computer camera to capture assess students' physical representations. I will conduct user studies with students and instructors to iteratively refine and pilot-test the application. User studies will yield a pilot-tested version of Chem Tutor that matches representation modes to activities based on conceptual and embodied affordances, gives adaptive feedback on physical representations, and adapts to students' learning progress.

4.3 Phase 2: Sequencing Physical and Virtual Representations

Phase 2 will investigate **Research question 2:** How do conceptual and embodied affordances affect which sequence of physical and virtual representations is most effective? Suppose Experiment 1 showed that students learn better about polarity with a virtual representation. Yet, because a physical representation has complementary benefits (e.g., making valency salient), a combination of both representation modes may be yet more effective. Because students may maintain the reasoning pattern afforded by the first representation mode, a sequence that starts with the representation mode that was most effective in Experiment 2 and then switches to the other representation mode may be most effective. Based on research on adaptive educational technologies, one might expect students to switch from one mode to the

other after they gained at least a moderate level of understanding of the target concept. *Experiment 2* will test these hypotheses with a between-subjects design. Students will be randomly assigned to four conditions: (1) physical or (2) virtual representations only, (3) an optimal sequence so that the first activity uses the representation mode that has matching embodied and/or conceptual affordances determined by Experiment 1 and the second activity uses the other mode, (4) or a random sequence of representation modes.

The assessments and analysis plans are identical to those described for Experiment 1. To collect think-aloud data that will augment the quantitative analyses in the same way as described above, at least five participants per condition will be asked to complete the homework assignment in my research lab while thinking aloud. Comparing Conditions 1 and 2 provides another empirical test of the hypotheses that emerged from the theoretical CTAs and will hence serve to replicate results from Experiment 1. Comparing Condition 3 to Conditions 1 and 2 tests whether combining representation modes based on an a priori assessment of complementary strengths is effective. Comparing Condition 3 to 4 tests the alternative hypothesis that any combination of physical and virtual representations enhances learning. Furthermore, the same analyses as in Experiment 1 will be used to investigate whether condition effects depend on students' prior chemistry knowledge and representation skills and on the nature of the concepts (abstractness, complexity, spatial nature), and whether representation skills mediate condition effects.

The experiment will be carried out as part of a homework assignment in introductory undergraduate chemistry courses at UW–Madison and MATC. An *a priori* power analysis with the same assumptions as above for *four* conditions showed that a minimum of $N = 136$ students are needed for $\beta = .80$. Because the targeted chemistry courses have an enrollment of 600-800 students, I expect no difficulties in recruitment.

4.4 Phase 3: Connection-Making between Physical and Virtual Representations

Phase 3 will investigate *Research question 3*: How does support to make connections between physical and virtual representations help students take advantage of conceptual and embodied affordances?

4.4.1 Development

I will draw on findings from Phases 1 and 2 to identify points at which students should switch from one representation mode to the other. I will develop connection-making activities for these switch points. The following vignette illustrates the hypothesized benefit of these activities. Suppose a student uses a virtual ball-and-stick model to learn about polarity. After initial practice on the concept of polarity, the cognitive model determines the student should switch to the physical ball-and-stick model. The student builds the physical model for carbon dioxide (a polar molecule), and a virtual ball-and-stick model depicts the student's actions at the same time. While building the physical model, the student notices the oxygen sphere has two holes. First, she is puzzled; she had assumed the number of holes show the number of valence electrons (but she knows that oxygen has six valence electrons). Looking at the virtual ball-and-stick model, she remembers having constructed bonds by dragging from the less to the more electronegative atom, which reminds her that oxygen has higher electronegativity than carbon. Suddenly, she realizes that the holes in physical ball-and-stick models show valency, not valence electrons: Atoms with low electronegativity that can "lose" two electrons *and* atoms with high electronegativity that can "gain" two electrons, so both have a valency of two! The connection-making activity helped her understand the physical representation. (Note this vignette illustrates the kinds of hypotheses Experiment 3 will test.)

To design such connection-making activities, I will use methods that have proven successful in prior work (Rau, under review; Rau, Aleven, Rummel, & Rohrbach, 2013). Five iterative steps are planned:

1. *Create low-fidelity prototype of connection-making activities* in which students interact with physical representations and a virtual representation reflects these interactions. Activities will engage embodied metaphors and motor actions identified in Phase 1. Virtual representations will reflect changes to physical representations in a wizard-of-Oz fashion: They will be controlled by a human behind the scene.
2. *Review and refine low-fidelity prototypes with chemistry instructors* to ensure that they enhance productive learning processes and align with chemistry curricula in the undergraduate courses.
3. *Conduct think-alouds on low-fidelity prototypes* to ensure they activate appropriate embodied and conceptual knowledge, engage intended metaphors and motor actions, and yield intuitive user experiences.

4. *Create and pilot-test high-fidelity prototypes.* My team will refine the application developed in Phase 2 so that they can display corresponding changes in the virtual representations.
5. *Finalize connection-making activities* that consolidate the lessons learned from pilot testing.

4.4.2 Experiments

Experiment 3 will use a between-subjects design with random assignment to two conditions: an optimal sequence of physical and virtual representations determined by Experiments 1 and 2 (1) without connection-making support, or (2) with connection-making support at the switch points. Condition 1 corresponds to Condition 3 of Experiment 2. Methods are identical to Experiment 2. Comparing the two conditions will test the hypothesis that connection-making support is effective. Further, the same tests as described above will investigate whether effects of connection-making support depend on students' prior chemistry knowledge and representation skills and on the nature of the concepts and whether representation skills mediate condition effects. Results and additional insights from the tutor log data and the think-alouds will serve to create the **final deliverable**: an intelligent blending version of Chem Tutor. As per the previous power analysis, Experiment 3 requires $N = 136$ students, recruited as in Experiment 2.

Experiment 4, detailed below in the Education Plan, will test whether an intelligent blending technology developed for a domain other than chemistry for instruction in a K-12 classroom is effective.

4.5 Contingency Plan for Inter-Connectedness of Experiments

So far, I described how *significant effects* found in each experiment inform the next experiments. In light of prior research, including my own research on the target chemistry concepts (Rau et al., 2016), it seems highly unlikely that the experiments will yield null-effects. Yet, the following provisions ensure the project's success in case of *non-significant effects*. First, even if there are null effects, the fact that the chemistry tests and the tutor log data test effects for each concept allows investigating whether any of the intelligent blending components are specific to particular types of concepts (e.g., concrete, complex, spatial). If this were the case, this finding would make an important theoretical contribution by establishing boundary conditions for the effectiveness of intelligent blending. It would make practical contributions to STEM education by identifying types of concepts for which matching, adapting, and connecting matters. Second, power analyses and repetition of conditions across experiments ensure such null-effects are "true" in the sense that no practically meaningful effect is to be found. Finally, identifying boundary conditions would imply that certain components of the intelligent blending framework would not be implemented for specific concepts. For example, if connection making is ineffective for polarity, Chem Tutor would not provide connection-making activities for polarity. Instructional time would then become available for other effective activities for this concept, thus increasing the effectiveness and the efficiency of the intervention as a whole. In sum, the inter-connectedness of the experiments enhances the project's capability to make important contributions, regardless of the specific outcome of each experiment.

5 Education Plan

As Figure 2 shows, education and research activities are intertwined so as to (1) enhance *undergraduate chemistry education*, (2) lay the groundwork for expanding the intelligent blending framework to *K-12 STEM education*, and (3) build capacities for *interdisciplinary research* on intelligent blending.

5.1 Enhance Undergraduate Chemistry Education

5.1.1 Develop Intelligent Blending Technologies that are Usable for Instructors and Students

To ensure my research will yield intelligent blending technologies that instructors and students experience as usable in their educational contexts, I will conduct the research in *partnership with instructors* at 2-year and 4-year colleges, specifically with advisory board members Dr. Moore and Dr. Landis at UW-Madison and Dr. Smith at MATC, as well as other instructors who agree to participate in the experiments. The goal of these partnerships is to inform the design of the intelligent blending version of Chem Tutor so that it aligns with the learning goals, systemic constraints, and deployment situations in varied educational contexts. Specifically, instructors will be involved in development activities via interviews that will serve to align Chem Tutor with their course curricula and teaching practices. Throughout the experiments, my team will monitor usability via interviews with instructors about issues they identified in using Chem

Tutor with their students, needs for additional guidance in using Chem Tutor, content alignment, and unsolicited observations of students. These data will inform updates to Chem Tutor between experiments. Findings will be consolidated in a manual that describes use practices with Chem Tutor. By making Chem Tutor usable for instructors as well as students, in particular by tailoring Chem Tutor to the different needs of instructors and students at 2-year and 4-year colleges, this partnership approach will increase the likelihood that instructors will adopt Chem Tutor and hence increase the impact of the proposed research.

Figure 2. Timeline for research activities and education activities.

5.1.2 Dissemination of Chem Tutor

To disseminate the new version of Chem Tutor, I will create www.iChemTutor.org. Instructors at 2-year and 4-year colleges will be involved in developing the website, so that I can tailor to needs of instructors in different contexts. The website will provide instruction for how to use Chem Tutor as a stand-alone platform or by incorporating it in learning management systems common at universities (e.g., Moodle). It will also show instructors how to retrieve information about their students' learning progress via Chem Tutor as a stand-alone platform or via their learning management systems. The website will offer videos that illustrate use-cases specific for 2- and 4-year colleges and tailored lesson plans. Users can order enhanced representations via the Institute of Chemical Education headed by advisory board member Dr. Moore. To broaden adoption of www.iChemTutor.org among instructors, I will organize demo sessions at practitioner conferences, such as meetings of the American Chemical Society, the Biennial Conference on Chemical Education, and the 2-Year College Chemistry Consortium. Finally, I will publish articles in practitioner oriented journals such as the *Journal of Chemical Education*.

5.2 Enhance STEM Education in K-12

Representations are important throughout education: first-graders learn about seasons with physical leaves and virtual animations of nutrient recycling in trees; fourth-graders learn about electric circuits with physical and virtual models. For example, consider the concepts of resistance and electron flow. A physical representation could be a dimmer switch that warms up as resistance increases (and light dims). Thus, the physical representation allows students to feel resistance. By contrast, virtual representations can illustrate electron flow changes resulting from increased resistance. The intelligent blending framework will make testable predictions about how to choose, adapt, and connect these representation modes.

One of my long-term career goals is to foster students' representation skills to enhance learning in K-12 STEM education. This research needs to be grounded in an understanding of how representations are used and of potential roadblocks students and instructors face in using representations (Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015). To lay groundwork for my long-term goals, I propose the following inter-connected activities.

5.2.1 *Teacher Workshop*

I will develop a workshop for K-12 teachers in a variety of STEM domains via UW–Madison’s Morgridge Institute for Research outreach program, which supports interactions among scientists, students, and instructors. The institute will recruit teachers for domains other than chemistry from districts with diverse and low-income populations and ensure the workshop counts toward ongoing teacher certification. The workshop has two goals. First, the goal is to enable instructors to analyze conceptual and embodied affordances of representation modes a priori and to develop lesson plans that combine these affordances in principled way. Second, the goal is to learn from teachers about what roadblocks they face when combining physical and virtual representations in their classrooms. Rather than using Chem Tutor, teachers will work with virtual and physical representations they typically use in their classrooms. My team will work with them to examine how principles provided by the intelligent blending framework might help them combine physical and virtual representations effectively. This will provide insights for my team on how an intelligent blending technology may be designed for a domain other than chemistry in an educational context other than 2-year and 4-year colleges. Prior to the workshop, I will ask teachers and their principals to identify potential roadblocks in using physical and virtual representations, to ensure the workshop addresses systemic demands. The workshop will take place five times over one semester. In the first meeting, teachers will use a theoretical CTA to develop lesson plans. During the semester, they will carry out the lesson plans. Between sessions, potential roadblocks will be monitored, documented, shared, and addressed in an online forum. Lesson plans will be revised and refined during workshop sessions. In going beyond common one-and-done workshops, this setup will allow teachers to transform their practice in situ. For evaluation of the workshop, teachers’ posts to the online forum serve as a formative mechanism, and a survey assessing their satisfaction serves as a summative mechanism.

The workshop will serve as a starting point for my research activities beyond the duration of this project because it will help me align the intelligent blending framework with needs and demands in STEM domains other than chemistry and for diverse K-12 education contexts. Further, the workshops may yield lasting partnerships with teachers interested in participating in my future research. Hence, the workshop will lay groundwork for my long-term career goal to partner with instructors to develop educational technologies that translate the intelligent blending framework into practice that transforms STEM education.

5.2.2 *Research Experience for Teachers*

One of the teachers from the workshop will be recruited to participate in an NSF-sponsored summer program at UW–Madison: Research Experience for Teachers (RET). I will recruit a teacher who teaches a subject other than chemistry at a school with diverse student populations. If none of the teachers from the workshop are interested in the RET, the RET program will assist in recruiting an alternative. The RET program allows teachers to work as part of a research group for six weeks during the summer to create learning modules for their classrooms. The teacher will also be part of a cohort of other teachers participating in the RET and will receive mentoring from an experienced teacher trainer from the RET. The RET teacher will partner with my research team to develop an intelligent blending intervention for his/her classroom, while addressing the potential roadblocks identified in the teacher workshop. To this end, the RET teacher will conduct a theoretical CTA to lay the groundwork for a cognitive model specific to her/his own domain. Then, with my team’s support, the teacher will build an ITS for his/her own domain, building on the principles that emerge from my research activities. Rather than developing new virtual representations, we will draw on virtual representations available on the web. After the six-week RET, the teacher will implement this intelligent blending intervention in his/her classroom. One goal of the RET is to provide teacher training. A second goal is to lay the groundwork for my future research on expanding the intelligent blending framework to K-12 education. A third goal is to broaden participation of diverse groups. A fourth goal is to establish a lasting partnership with the teacher to build capacities for my research beyond this 5-year project. A fifth goal is to augment the dissemination plan (see below) based on the RET teacher’s insights. *Experiment 4* will evaluate whether the RET activity achieves these goals. Using a quasi-experimental design, the experiment will test whether the intelligent blending intervention leads to higher learning gains on a domain knowledge test, compared to a class that did not use the inter-

vention. The experiment will be conducted at the teacher's school following the summer program. Students' learning will be assessed using a domain knowledge test that contains standardized test items that align with relevant content standards. My research team will assist the teacher with the experiment activities. We will conduct the analyses using the same methods as described for Experiments 1-3.

5.2.3 *Dissemination of Intelligent Blending Framework in K-12*

Insights from the teacher workshop and the RET will be consolidated on www.iChemTutor.org. Specifically, a K-12 section will be added to the website, which will offer the following functions. First, my team will offer in-person workshops for teachers who want to implement the intelligent blending intervention, to be held at their schools. Second, it will provide a manual tailored to K-12 contexts, developed based on the RET. The manual will provide lesson plans, lessons learned about how to respond to questions by students and parents, etc. Third, a series of short videos will illustrate successful use-cases in classrooms. Finally, the website will offer a forum for continued exchange among teachers and my team.

5.3 **Enhance Interdisciplinary Research on Educational Technologies with Representations**

Research on educational technologies that help students learn with visual representations requires an interdisciplinary perspective. I propose three activities to build an interdisciplinary research community.

5.3.1 *Interdisciplinary Educational Technology Course for Undergraduate and Graduate Students*

I will develop a new course for undergraduate and graduate students on user-centered design of educational technologies. To recruit interdisciplinary student groups, I will advertise courses through the DELTA program and the Center for the Integration of Research, Teaching, and Learning Network at UW–Madison. These NSF-sponsored programs build communities of interdisciplinary researchers and practitioners. In a semester-long course project, students will design an educational technology for a particular domain and educational context. To this end, they have to investigate the needs of students and teachers in terms of learning goals and constraints of the educational context (e.g., large classrooms). Teams will involve at least one student with a technology background and one student from an education field.

I will teach this course twice; before and after the teacher workshop. The first iteration will allow me to contact teachers to partner with students who will develop technologies for their needs. These teachers will be invited to participate in the workshop (among others, see 5.2.1). In addition, students may be partnered with an instructor at the UW–Madison or MATC. In the second iteration of the course, teams may again be partnered with a teacher from the workshop or with an instructor at UW–Madison or MATC. The course will use examples from the user-centered approach described above. The second iteration of the course will be augmented with examples and lessons learned from the teacher workshop and RET.

One goal of this course is to equip students with skills to conduct user-centered studies that inform the development of educational technologies. Another goal is to help students collaborate in interdisciplinary teams. A third goal is to establish partnerships with instructors in K-16 contexts. Besides standard course evaluations, I will use surveys to assess students' views on interdisciplinary collaborations. I will work with the UW–Madison Teaching Academy to obtain feedback on managing interdisciplinary group work.

5.3.2 *Mentoring in My Research Lab*

I will mentor undergraduate and graduate students in my research lab. Undergraduate students will be recruited from the UW–Madison Undergraduate Research Scholars program and from the Wisconsin Center for Education Research Minority Student Achievement Network, which seek to enhance diversity and equity. One goal in mentoring students is to *enhance STEM education* by including students from diverse socioeconomic and disciplinary backgrounds. Participating in my research offers opportunities to learn about the importance of interdisciplinary research to develop effective educational technologies. Further, including students from STEM domains will help achieve my long-term career goal to improve education in STEM domains beyond chemistry. A second goal is to equip students with skills to *bridge theories of learning with technology development*. I will recruit students with backgrounds in psychology, education, and computer science. They will learn how the interplay among rigorous experiments, user-centered design studies, and technology development can yield new knowledge about how people learn while developing technologies that address real educational needs and are usable in real K-16 educational

contexts (Rau, Aleven et al., 2013). Third, my goal is to *close the loop* between fine-grained educational data and iterative refinement of educational psychology theory. I will train students in using educational data mining techniques to understand how learning processes unfold over time and to use these insights to inform educational technology design. The fast growth of educational data mining research illustrates the need to develop methods for using these data to develop theories about learning.

To evaluate my mentoring activities, I will ask students involved in my lab to fill out an anonymous survey at the end of each semester on preferred research activities and mentoring they received.

5.3.3 Dissemination of Intelligent Blending Framework to Interdisciplinary Research Communities

I will disseminate the intelligent blending framework via www.intelligent-representations.org. The website will be a knowledge base and tool kit for incorporating physical representations into educational technologies. The website will connect researchers from fields such as educational psychology, cognitive science, STEM education, and human-computer interaction. By making all research methodology steps and research outcomes available, the website will enable others to investigate new research questions about the intelligent blending framework. To disseminate results from my research, I will target a variety of interdisciplinary conferences and journals, including international conferences on Artificial Intelligence in Education, Educational Data Mining, Intelligent Tutoring Systems, and Cognitive Science Society, and the *Journal of Educational Psychology*, the *Journal of Learning Sciences*, and the *Journal of Cognitive Sciences*. I will also organize a workshop at the International Conference of the Learning Sciences in 2020. In disseminating my research to *interdisciplinary research communities*, I seek to stimulate further research on the intelligent blending framework, which will in turn improve STEM education.

6 Personnel

The personnel on the team have expertise in ITSs, learning sciences and technology, educational psychology, and chemistry education and the necessary experience to succeed in the proposed research. Principal investigator (PI) **Dr. Rau** is an assistant professor in educational psychology and computer sciences at UW–Madison. She is co-investigator on an NSF NRT-DESE grant (LUCID): A project-focused cross-disciplinary graduate training program for data-enabled research in human and machine learning and teaching (DGE-1545481). Under an NSF grant (REESE-21851-1-1121307, Award 0910010, PIs Dr. Aleven and Dr. Rummel), her research yielded principles for the use of virtual representations, and she developed the Fractions Tutor, an ITS that leads to significant learning gains in fractions, available at <https://fractions.cs.cmu.edu>. Dr. Rau has extensive experience conducting controlled classroom experiments, using user-centered design methods, and complex statistical modeling with multiple measures (e.g., eye-tracking data, verbal data, tutor log data, learning outcomes). Over 2,000 undergraduate chemistry students have participated in Dr. Rau’s research on Chem Tutor. Dr. Rau’s work has been repeatedly recognized at competitive research conferences and was published in the journal of *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. She has published in international journals including the journals of *Learning and Instruction*, *Educational Psychology*, *Educational Psychology Review*, and *Computers and Education*.

Dr. Rau will lead the project, providing scientific direction and overseeing research and development activities, and relations with instructors. She will serve as academic advisor to undergraduate and graduate students. One graduate student with background in chemistry education will be funded through this project. An additional graduate student with background in educational psychology will be recruited from the NSF-funded Research Traineeship “LUCID” program. LUCID is highly synergistic with the proposed project, as students receive extensive interdisciplinary training by working on a project at the intersection of educational psychology, computer science, and engineering. Students will develop ITS activities, conduct experiments, and analyze data. A research programmer, supervised by Dr. Rau, will develop ITS functionalities that will handle interactions with physical representations via computer cameras. Dr. Rau will rely on project management resources provided by the Wisconsin Center for Education Research.

Dr. Rau will organize full-day virtual advisory board meetings twice a year. **Dr. Stieff**, associate professor in chemistry at the University of Illinois, Chicago, will provide advice on the development of educational technologies for chemistry learning. **Dr. Hegarty**, professor in psychological and brain sciences at the University of California, Santa Barbara, will provide advice on conceptual affordances of physical

and virtual representations in chemistry. **Dr. Abrahamson**, associate professor in the University of California, Berkeley Graduate School of Education, will provide advice on embodied affordances of instructional activities. **Dr. Puntambekar**, professor in educational psychology at UW–Madison, will provide feedback on planned contributions to distributed scaffolding research. **Dr. Linn**, professor in educational psychology at the University of California, Berkeley, director of the NSF-funded Technology-Enhanced Learning Center, will provide feedback on conducting research with educational technologies in real classroom contexts. Three advisory board members will assist the PI in aligning the Chem Tutor curriculum with courses at 2-year and 4-year colleges and in finding courses in which to carry out the planned experiments. **Dr. Moore**, professor in chemistry at UW–Madison, is the director of the Institute for Chemical Education and was the editor of the *Journal of Chemical Education*. The Institute for Chemical Education will serve as a hub for the dissemination of the accompanying materials for Chem Tutor. **Dr. Landis**, professor in Chemistry at UW–Madison, has over 30 years of teaching experience and recently published a book on chemical bonding. They have agreed to assist the PI in finding courses for the experiments. **Dr. Smith**, instructor at MATC, agreed to conduct experiments in her chemistry courses.

7 Intellectual Merit

The proposed research activities will provide a theory that describes mechanisms by which conceptual and embodied affordances of physical and virtual representations affect students' learning of representation skills and domain knowledge. This theory will extend existing *embodied learning theory* by helping us understand how embodied affordances of different representation modes interact with their conceptual affordances. This research will also contribute to theories of *distributed scaffolding* and *hybrid models*, yielding principles for integrating traditional, hands-on activities with virtual, technology-based resources in an intelligent and adaptive way. It will extend research on *connection making* among representations that has mostly focused on virtual representations. It will extend research on *digitally enhanced representations* by testing whether connection making among virtual and physical representations of the same type is effective. This project will contribute to research on *representation skills* by investigating how enhancing students' representation skills helps them learn domain knowledge in STEM. By adding an embodied cognition perspective to this research, it will bring together two mostly separate lines of research. This project will also contribute to research on *adaptive educational technologies* by blending multiple learning modes in a way that can be deployed in mainstream classrooms while taking advantage of their adaptive capabilities. Finally, this project will establish a new line of research on *intelligent blending* that allows educational technologies to adapt to embodied knowledge.

8 Broader Impacts

My 5-year CAREER project will yield a design framework for a new genre of educational technologies that intelligently blend physical and virtual representations while adapting to individual students' needs. It will yield a new intelligent blending technology designed for chemistry instruction at 2-year and 4-year colleges. Two-year colleges are key access points for *underrepresented minorities* to higher education (Bailey, Hoard, Nugent, & Geary, 2012; NRC, 2012), yet, they often lack innovative educational technologies tailored to their needs (NRC, 2012). Because representation skills are a crucial aspect of students' success in chemistry, and because students' failures in chemistry courses are often related to low representation skills, the proposed activities may *significantly enhance chemistry learning*. Undergraduate chemistry is a gatekeeper for many STEM careers (Karatjas, 2013). The New York Times (2011) Top 10 list of jobs with worker shortages includes several that involve chemistry. Hence, my research may increase economic prosperity. The proposed research activities will also improve *broader educational practice* by giving instructors tools to combine activities with and without technologies, and to help students connect transition between these modes. The planned education activities will take a first step toward expanding this research to other *STEM domains in K-12* contexts. In these activities, I will work with teachers from schools with diverse and low-income populations. By sharing lessons learned from these activities with practitioners, this project will help close the loop between research and practice. The interrelated nature of the education activities allows for building lasting connections with instructors in K-16 contexts, so as to facilitate my line of work on intelligent blending beyond this 5-year grant.